

FROM TRADITION TO TRANSITION: EXPLORING ACCULTURATION LEVEL AMONG WOMEN MIGRANTS IN BUKIDNON

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the level of acculturation and cultural roles of Ivatan women migrants in Bukidnon, focusing on their settlement and post-migration adaptation. Fifty-one first-generation Ivatan women were surveyed using interviews and an adapted acculturation scale. Findings reveal that these women, residing in Malinao, Kalilangan, Bukidnon for over 30 years, retained a strong ties to their language and ethnic identity. Their overall acculturation level remains low, particularly regarding language and ethnic identity preservation. Based on these findings, the study concludes that a robust ethnic identity plays a significant role in resisting external cultural influences. However, the preservation and transmission of Ivatan culture are hindered by interpersonal dynamics and technological advancements. To address these challenges, the study recommends a sociological approach to further investigate the cultural dynamics of migrant Ivatan women, with a specific focus on language and intangible cultural heritage. Enhanced research efforts are proposed to uncover and document the tangible and intangible aspects of Ivatan culture that may be at risk of fading. This study underscores the importance of understanding and supporting the cultural preservation efforts of migrant Ivatan communities through comprehensive sociological inquiry and targeted preservation initiatives.

Keywords: *Acculturation, Migration, Ethnic Identity, Language, Culture Preservation*

INTRODUCTION

Resettlement areas in the Philippines are attributed to the government's economic policy of distribution of lands, particularly in rural areas and vast fertile areas in Mindanao, for its utilization as agricultural areas and the eventual productivity and economic growth of such localities. Several farm projects located in Mindanao were offered to peasant farmers in Luzon during the Magsaysay administration (Horakova, 1971). In 1955, the Philippine Government declared that certain parts of Mindanao would be a "Promised Land" to any interested farmers willing to settle and cultivate the area. This motivated farmers from different parts of the archipelago to resettle in

Mindanao since they will be given their lands to farm. Bukidnon was then one of the declared provinces. This program was undertaken by the LASEDECO or Land Settlement Development Corporation. The Ivatans are one of the settlers along with the other groups from Luzon, Visayas, and nearby provinces in Misamis Oriental (Santiago, 1979). This series of migrations contributed to making some communities a multicultural society. The intricate and multifaceted impact of migrations on creating a multicultural society can be observed through various lenses. One of the most evident impacts is the demographic shift brought about by migration, leading to a rich diversity of ethnicities, languages, and cultural traditions within a society. This blending of different backgrounds enriches the social fabric and presents opportunities for individuals to learn from and embrace a wide array of cultural experiences.

In Ivatan culture, the role of women was to help perpetuate the economic status of the entire family or society (Buendia, n.d.). Division of labor based on gender is uncommon, whereby men and women have to share in all family activities at home or on a farm. In contrast, Ivatans in Malinao are aware of the present cultural changes that they are experiencing. The traditions, values systems, practices, and even their language are losing popularity among the young Ivatans.

These changes are inevitable in any society where different groups and cultures are intertwined. This process of change in culture is commonly referred to as *acculturation*. *Acculturation* refers to the exchange of cultural features that results when groups come into continuous first hand contact; the cultural patterns of both groups have changed, but the groups remain distinct (Berry, 2006). This study aims to better understand how migration affects the acculturation process of women as they fulfill their roles as custodians of distinct cultural practices.

Research Questions

This study would like to assess the level of acculturation among Ivatan women and present their experiences as custodians of culture. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of Ivatan women?

2. What is the level of acculturation of Ivatan women according to:
 - a. Language spoken; and
 - b. Ethnic Identity?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Malinao, an urban barangay of the Municipality of Kalilangan in Bukidnon. Kalilangan is one of the 20 municipalities in Bukidnon situated in the Southern part of the Province. It is a 2nd class municipality covering a total land area of 28,414. 10 hectares. The town is bounded on the North by the municipality of Talakag, on the South by the Province of Lanao del Sur, on the East by the Municipality of Pangantucan, and on the Southwest by the Province of Lanao del Sur. It is further politically subdivided into 14 barangays, 4 of which are urban and 10 are rural barangays. Malinao is an urbanizing barangay in the Northwestern portion of the municipality of Kalilangan. It covers the biggest land area, which comprises 30.02% of the municipality. It is bounded by SVF Forchacu II in the North, Kili-Kili in the South, Barangay Canituan in the East, and Bumbaran in the West. It was created in 1958 through the NARRA settlement program. It has a total land area of 8,532.14 hectares with 349 titled farm lots. It is composed of 12 Puroks. The barangay is known for its hilly and rolling slopes with mountainous roads approaching the Poblacion.

Respondents

The subject–respondents of this study are the 50 first-generation Ivatan women migrants. Specifically, the respondents are the Ivatan women who were born in Batanes. The respondents are representatives from two communities with large numbers of Ivatan residents. The respondents of the study were obtained from the updated list from the Barangay Captain. Since the respondents are limited to the first-generation migrants, they were identified using snowball sampling. The 50 identified respondents included 41 women from the Poblacion of Malinao and nine from Imbariz, a barrio of Barangay Malinao.

The Instruments

The study used an adopted acculturation scale to measure ethnic identity. It also used the interview to measure the extent of acculturation. The first part of the instrument consists of questions from 1 to 8 to gather data on the socio-demographic characteristics of the Ivatan women. Part 2 comprises questions adopted from Santiago's study (1979) to draw demographic information upon their arrival in Malinao. It also includes questions on the reasons why they decided to come and settle in Malinao, Kalilangan. Part 3 measured the extent of acculturation on language using the adopted and modified acculturation scale of the HCHS/SOL Sociocultural Questionnaire. Section B includes

The Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure, adopted from Phinney (1992), which was used to measure the extent of acculturation on ethnic identity. The extent of acculturation will be determined using 5 point scale, ranging from strongly disagree(1), agree (2), neutral (3), disagree (4) to strongly agree (5) responses.

Scoring Procedure

Responses to the questions in parts I, II, and III were used to determine the Ivatan women's role as custodians of culture. It will be further utilized to correlate with the extent of acculturation of Ivatan women in language and MEIM scale. On the MEIM (Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure), the researcher adopted the scoring procedure presented by Phinney(1992). Ethnic identity is obtained when the total score is derived by reversing negative items (indicated by "R), summing across items, and obtaining the mean (Items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8R, 10R, 11, 12,13,14,16, 18, and 20). The result will reveal affirmation and belongingness. It will also measure the individual ethnic identity in relation to their acculturation.

To measure the level of acculturation, the following adopted and modified instruments are utilized to measure language spoken and ethnic identity. A separate measurement was used to assess the cultural knowledge of the respondents.

The following rating range and qualitative description were utilized to measure the level of acculturation. The measurement of acculturation level is based on language spoken and Ethnic Identity.

Weight Points	Mean Values	Description
5	4.21 -5.00	Very High Acculturation
4	3.41 – 4.20	High Acculturation
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Acculturation
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low Acculturation
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Acculturation

From the measurement, a very high acculturation indicates adopting the host society's language. Meanwhile, very low acculturation indicates the retention of the respondents' language (Ivatan) as it is frequently used in daily activities. As reflected in the study of Phinney (1992), in assessing ethnic identity, a description of very high acculturation indicates a weak ethnic identity, while a very low acculturation indicates a

strong ethnic identity.

Treatment of Data

The data was analyzed using the SPSS (v.19) or Statistical Packages for Social Sciences. The acculturation level for language spoken and ethnic identity was determined using the mean and standard deviation. Meanwhile, the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents were presented using frequency distribution and percentage.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of the Repondents

Table 1 displays the frequency distribution of the respondents' history of migration.

Table 1 Frequency distribution of the respondents history of settlement

Years of Settlement	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1951 – 1955	1	2%
1956 – 1960	31	62%*
1961 – 1965	10	20%
1966 – 1970	1	2%
1971 – 1975	5	10%
1976 – 1980	2	4%
Civil Status		
Child	14	28%
Single	13	26%
Married	21	42%*
Widow	2	4%
Number of Children		
0 – 3	19	38%
4 – 7	5	10%
8 – 10	1	2%
N/A (child)	25	50%*
Occupation		
Farmer	28	56%*
Others	14	28%
Housemaid	6	12%
Homemaker	2	4%
Monthly Income		
500 and Below	4	8%
500 – 1,000	7	14%
1,001 – 1,500	4	8%
Undetermined	35	70%*
Information about the settlement		
From parents & relatives	37	74%*

From neighbors	9	18%
From community leaders	4	8%
Decision to settle		
Discussed with family members	28	56%*
Advice from parents & relatives	13	26%
Others	6	12%
By yourself	3	6%
Reasons for settlement		
To own a land	25	50%*
Others	10	20%
To have adventure	7	14%
Conditions in the place of origin was difficult	4	8%
To go with relatives who decide to settle	2	4%
To go with parents	2	4%
Total	50	100%

The Ivatan Women's level of acculturation according to language used

Table 2 displays the acculturation level of the respondents based on the language spoken.

Table 2 The level of acculturation based on language spoken

Statement	Frequency	\bar{x}	Qualitative Description
In general, what language(s) are the movies, T.V. and radio programs you prefer to watch and listen to?	Only Ivatan	0	Very High Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano /Tagalog	4	
	Both equally	2	
	Cebuano /Tagalog better than Ivatan	11	
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	33*	
If you could choose your children's friends you would want them to be...	Only Ivatan	6	Moderate Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	4	
	Both Equally	40*	
	Cebuano /Tagalog better than Ivatan	0	
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	0	
What language(s) do you usually speak with your friends?	Only Ivatan	3	Low Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano /Tagalog	22*	
	Both equally	21	
	Cebuano /Tagalog better than Ivatan	3	
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	1	
In what languages do you read and speak?	Only Ivatan	4	Low Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	24*	
	Both Equally	14	
	Cebuano/Tagalog better than Ivatan	8	
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	0	
The persons you visit or who visit you are...	Only Ivatan	9	Low Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	21*	
	Both Equally	20	
	Cebuano/Tagalog better than Ivatan	0	
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	0	
Your close friends are...	Only Ivatan	2	Low Acculturation
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	28*	
	Both Equally	20	

	Cebuano/Tagalog better than Ivatan	0		
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	0		
You prefer going to social gatherings/parties at which people are...	Only Ivatan	9		
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	21*		
	About half and half	20	2.22	Low
	Both Equally	0		Acculturation
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	0		
What language(s) do you usually speak at home?	Only Ivatan	13		
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	24*		
	Both Equally	7	2.14	Low
	Cebuano/Tagalog better than Ivatan	5		Acculturation
	Only Cebuano/Tagalog	1		
In which language(s) do you usually think?	Only Ivatan	45*		
	Ivatan better than Cebuano /Tagalog	2		
	Both equally	1	1.22	Very Low
	Cebuano /Tagalog better than Ivatan	1		Acculturation
	Only Cebuano /Tagalog	1		
What was the language(s) you used as a child?	Only Ivatan	46*		
	Ivatan better than Cebuano/Tagalog	3		
	Both Equally	0	1.12	Very Low
	Cebuano/Tagalog better than Ivatan	1		Acculturation
	Only Cebuano/Tagalog	0		
	Over all	50	1.85	Low Acculturation

N= 50 * rank first

The Ivatan Women's level of acculturation according to Ethnic identity

Another measure of acculturation used in this study is the Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure. The summary of responses is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of Responses on the Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure

Statements	\bar{X}	S.D.	Qualitative Description
I am happy that I am a member of the group I belong to	4.92	.27	Very Low Acculturation
I have a strong sense of belonging to my own ethnic group.	4.80	.45	Very Low Acculturation
I feel good about my cultural or ethnic background.	4.78	.50	Very Low Acculturation
I have a lot of pride in my ethnic group and its accomplishments.	4.64	.52	Very Low Acculturation
I am active in organizations or social groups that include mostly members of my own ethnic group.	4.58	.70	Very Low Acculturation
I feel a strong attachment towards my own ethnic group.	4.56	.54	Very Low Acculturation
I participate in cultural practices of my own group, such as special food, music, or customs.	4.30	.67	Very Low Acculturation
I understand pretty well what my ethnic group membership means to me, in terms of how to relate to my own group and other groups.	4.18	.62	Low Acculturation
I have spent time trying to find out more about my own ethnic group, such as its history, traditions, and customs.	4.08	.56	Low Acculturation
I have a clear sense of my ethnic background and what it means for me.	4.0	.80	Low Acculturation
I think a lot about how my life will be affected by my ethnic	3.92	.80	

group membership.			Low Acculturation
I am involved in activities with people from other ethnic groups.	3.88	.71	Low Acculturation
In order to learn more about my ethnic background, I have often talked to other people about my ethnic group.	3.80	.94	Low Acculturation
I don't try to become friends with people from other ethnic groups.	3.68	.68	Low Acculturation
I sometimes feel it would be better if different ethnic groups didn't try to mix together.	3.46	.90	Low Acculturation
I like meeting and getting to know people from ethnic groups other than my own.	3.42	.97	Low Acculturation
I enjoy being around people from ethnic groups other than my own.	3.28	1.0	Moderate Acculturation
I often spend time with people from ethnic groups other than my own.	3.02	1.0	Moderate Acculturation
I really have not spent much time trying to learn more about the culture and history of my ethnic group.	2.72	1.0	Moderate Acculturation
I am not very clear about the role of my ethnicity in my life.	2.52	1.23	Low Acculturation
Overall	3.92	.74	Low Acculturation

Legend:

- 4.21 – 5.00 Very Low Acculturation
- 3.41 – 4.20 Low Acculturation
- 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Acculturation
- 1.81 – 2.60 High acculturation
- 1.00 – 1.80 – Very High acculturation

DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Years of settlement. Ivatan migration was said to be a family group migration. After the first batch of respondents arrived in Malinao from 1961 to 1965, followed by 1971-1975 and 1976–1980. In the case of a respondent who came as early as 1951- 1955, this is the case of the remaining original Ivatan settlers.

Civil Status. The civil status of respondents upon their arrival in Malinao is summarized as follows: the majority of the respondents were married, and some were single. Interestingly, a significant number of respondents were still a child when they arrived in Malinao to join their parents and relatives. Arriving very young in Malinao had some implications for the acculturation of the Ivatans. Two of the respondents were widowed when they arrived in Malinao. Single and unmarried parents were considered eligible settlers as long as they had dependents. This may be because the government may have relied on Ivatan's *bayanihan* system. As discussed earlier, the absence or death of a husband or a man in the family may not be a significant concern for the widowed wife and her children. In an Ivatan community, everybody is there to help without anyone asking. The Ivatan men were willing to help a widowed Ivatan tend her farm and

help the orphaned children. The availability of men to help is, of course, contributed by women who can tend their farms as efficiently as men. Nobody will run out of well-meaning helping hands in the Ivatan farms.

Number of children. The majority of the respondents have children ranging from 0 – 3, followed by those who had 4-7 children when they arrived in the settlement. According to Escalona's letters, their parents brought these children aboard LST (Landing Ship Troop) from Batanes to their settlement area. Two pregnant women were also with the group. Based on the documents, to be qualified as settlers, there had to be a family head for every family, regardless of whether it was a man or a woman. Interestingly, some respondents arrived in Malinao as children. This partly explains the "low level of acculturation" among the Ivatan since Malinao is isolated from the rest of the Kalilangan area. In one interview, a respondent recalled that it was in Malinao where she had learned the Ivatan language.

Occupation. The occupation of the respondents when they were still in Batanes was mainly farming. This is relatively true because in Batanes, farming is the Ivatan's primary livelihood (Dayo, 2011). Indeed, they have been considered as settlers because they are farmers. Also, a good number of respondents worked as house help in Batanes. Some respondents had been in Manila or had been house help for foreigners in Batanes. This implies that aside from farming, some respondents consider house help to be one of the options to support their daily needs. This is because life is hard in Batanes, the respondents would always exclaim. A small piece of land is not enough to support a family's daily needs. Some stayed at home while the others were young enough to work. Although they might be very young to work for an earning, they had numerous tasks like *magpastol* (grazing the herds), *mag inadlaw* (being paid daily for labor on the farm), accompanying their parents in the farm, and running errands whenever needed. This also contributes to the Ivatan's upbringing, commonly called "*raised on the farm.*" It is a practice that contributed to the making of an Ivatan woman farmer since farming is a task for everybody and everyone in the family. This was also observed in the study of Baretto (2012) among the Bukidnons; the enculturation of children is through the effort of the parents who brought them to the farm to observe what their parents and other adults are doing. The respondents supported this when they said, "yan man ang Nakita naming sa aming mga magulang" (that was what we observed from our parents), referring to the practice of going to the farm.

Monthly Income. The Ivatans are hesitant to disclose how much they earn, and the researcher could not determine how much they earned when they were still in Batanes. According to the key informant, the Ivatans would hesitate if asked about their income; most of them find it uncomfortable to talk about their income. Also, some respondents had incomes that ranged from P500 to P1,000. This includes those who work as house helpers, nannies, or selling the garden's produce.

Information about the settlement. Table 1 shows that most respondents knew about the settlement from their parents and relatives. This might be because a considerable number of the respondents were still very young during the settlement. As

claimed by the respondents who *had known the settlement from a community leader*, the arrival of Ivatans in Bukidnon was through the effort of Marcos Escalona, a community leader in Batanes (Santiago, 1979). Aside from that, having a family or being with a family was a requirement to be qualified as a settlers. Ivatans are known to be closely knit (Batanes: Born of Fire and Water, 2011).

Decision to Settle. The decision to become settlers was mainly attributed to a *discussion with family members*. In comparison, *advice from parents and relatives comes second*. Only a few *decided for themselves*, while others decided to settle because they were still young and could not decide; some *had come with their relatives*. Their responses are supported by literature and observation in the community, that the Ivatans are family oriented. They work and live as a family. Their bayanihan system might have emerged from their close family ties. One respondent said, "*huwag ipagwalang bahala ang mga kamag-anak*" (Do not turn your back on relatives), a confirmation of deep concern with members of the Ivatan community. This supported the study of Johnson (1996) on reasons why people migrate, in the case of the Ivatans, Johnson classified it as social migration, whereby social migration entails moving to a better quality of life or to move closer with family and friends.

Reasons for settlement. From the respondents, most of them *had come to settle in Malinao to own a land*, a natural resource that is so scarce in Batanes. In the letter of Marcos Escalona to President Magsaysay, he pleaded the cause of Ivatan peasants, as their hard life in Batanes is no better than the heavily tenanted areas in Central Luzon, that rice is considered as golden cereal and can be served only during special occasions. This portrays the hard life in Batanes that prompted them to leave Batanes and look for a greener pasture. As observed, the migration of Ivatans in Luzon or any parts of the country had been widespread. This could be attributed to a hard life on a frequently stormed island. Some respondents recalled how terrible it was during the storm. The storm often wipes out the root crops and other produce.

Thus, the history of Ivatan migration was significantly contributed by pull factors. As claimed by social science scholars, for most migrants, "pull factors" are stronger than "push factors". This implies that the hope of a better life in a new place will outweigh the worry of what they had to leave behind (Weichold, 2010; Berry, 2006; Deshingkar, et al., 2004; Richerson as cited by Ward, 1992). Also, in the study of Johnson (1996) Ivatans' migration is also referred to as economic migration, where migration may involve finding work or looking for a greener pasture. Baretto (2012) also mentioned that that was the common reason migrants from Luzon, Visayas, and some parts of Misamis came to Bukidnon. The history of Ivatan migration may create a clear picture of what encouraged them to come and settle and their demographic characteristics. This has something to do with the respondents after years of settlement.

Language is considered one of the most essential components of ethnic identity (Kang, 2006) and has been commonly and widely assessed across acculturation instruments (Phinney, 1992). The Ivatans' language is of Austronesian origin; it has some Spanish influence and some tone of Chinese origin (Batanes Born of Fire, 2000). It was

known as Chirin nu Ibatan, otherwise known as Ivatan. The table further displays their level of acculturation in terms of language spoken.

The Ivatan Women's level of acculturation according to language used

To specifically examine the Ivatan women's acculturation level in terms of language spoken, the following were discussed. The respondents' overall acculturation level was *low acculturation*. This would mean that in terms of language, a low acculturation means that the Ivatan language was still widely used among the first generation migrants. In another manner, this would also entail that their language shows signs of declining. This could be influenced by the languages in movies, TV, and radio programs they prefer to watch and listen to, as well as languages that are not Ivatan.

Besides, Ivatan movies, T.V. and radio programs are unavailable in Malinao. This does not mean they would prefer watching non-Ivatan movies, but it is because they do not have much choice in what to watch. Consequently, on the statement "*If you could choose your children's friends you would want them to be with*", they had *moderate acculturation*. This implies that some respondents want their children to socialize more with Ivatan friends. Having an Ivatan friend might be an advantage for the enculturation of the young Ivatan. The idea that their children had friends who are also Ivatans has given them peace of mind. The researcher's observation in Malinao affirms this. During fieldwork, It was observed that the almost empty streets in Malinao show that the young Ivatans are not usually seen loitering in the streets. The people, including the young Ivatans, go to school or the farm. If not, they are at home; they never stay in the streets. This could be attributed to the Ivatan women bringing their children to the farm.

For many years in Kalilangan, the researcher never heard of a delinquent Ivatan. Although, in some situations, some respondents would allow their children to have friends who are non-Ivatans, provided that they are good friends. In one interview, a respondent said "*Kahit na sino ang gusto nilang kaibigan, ok lang.*" (Whatever friends they had, its ok), This can also be observed from some respondents that whoever their children would like to be with would be up to them, which is a form of leniency to children's wishes. This kind of leniency could lead to a series of intermarriages of young generation Ivatans to non-Ivatans. They may prefer having an Ivatan-in-law, but it is still the children's decision that prevails.

Interestingly, the level of acculturation where most of the respondents got *low acculturation* are as follows: a) languages they usually speak with friends; b) the persons they visit and their visitors c) their close friends; d) attended to parties and social gatherings with Ivatans; e) languages they read and speak; and languages they usually speak at home. In the study of Santiago (1979), among the Ivatans in Malinao, she noticed that inside or outside the house, the dialect used was Ivatan and Pilipino was resorted when non-Ivatan are present. Cebuano was used with the guest who belonged to Visayan group. She also observed that during the early settlement, it is not uncommon for Ivatans to use their dialect even in non-Ivatans' presence. The researcher observed that Ivatan dialect is common only among the elders. When the young Ivatans were asked

how fluent they are with the language, their reply was, "*hindi po masyado marunong, yun lang kadalasang ginagamit na salita*", (I knew only a few Ivatan words, usually those that are commonly used in daily conversation).

In the same way, the respondents had *low acculturation* on the person they visited, their close friends, and attendance at Ivatan parties and social gatherings. These imply that they still maintained close relationships with their Ivatan friends and relatives. As observed, Ivatan homes are nearby. In terms of having close friends, the respondents scored low on a acculturation scale. This indicates that most of their close friends are Ivatan's.

In terms of socialization, the questionnaire shows that attendees are Ivatans. In terms of socialization, the questionnaire shows that the Ivatans are not highly acculturated. The Ivatans still prefer to visit Ivatan friends and relatives. Interestingly, in choosing their children's friends they had *moderate acculturation*. According to the respondents it does not matter if their children will have an Ivatan or an *Ipula* friend. Whatever preferences their children have for their friends, they would gladly accept it. Also, they had *low acculturation* on *languages they speak with friends; languages they read and speak; and languages they speak at home*. This supports their responses that they surround themselves more with Ivatan friends and acquaintances

A *low acculturation* on the languages spoken at home entails that Ivatan language was still widely spoken by the respondents in their homes. The results also entail that, although not extensively, the Ivatan language is commonly used in and outside of their homes with their Ivatan family members and friends. During the researcher's visit to the respondents, she observed that the house was always filled with grandchildren. If the elders talk with adult members children, as well as with the other elders, they use the Ivatan language. However, when they talk with their grandchildren, they usually use Tagalog or Cebuano.

Most of the respondents claimed that their grandchildren could not understand Ivatan, so they had to use Tagalog. One respondent claimed that, "*Ang mga apo ko hindi na makaintindi ng Ivatan*" (My grandchildren do not understand Ivatan). This could be because the language used in school is Cebuano, and most of the people in the community are composed of Cebuano, Ilonggo, Ilocano, and Maranao. The lingua franca used in the community is Cebuano.

Meanwhile, they had a *very low acculturation* in terms of how frequently they used the Ivatan language when *they think* and the *language they used as a child*. As first-generation migrants, their language orientation is similar to that of Batanes origin. However this does not mean that all of the respondents exclusively used Ivatan during their childhood because some had been using Tagalog or English. This is because Manila is one of the most common places an Ivatan would visit when they travel out of Batanes. This shows that the respondents had a deep appreciation of their culture. Thus, language is an important factor in preserving one's culture and an individual's sense of ethnicity.

The Ivatan Women's level of acculturation according to Ethnic identity

Another measure of acculturation used in this study is the Multigroup Ethnic Identity Measure. The summary of responses is presented in Table 11. The data reveals that the respondents had *low acculturation* on ethnic identity. This means the respondents have a strong sense of affirmation and belongingness to their ethnic group.

From the data, the respondents had *very low acculturation* on being happy that they are members of the Ivatan group. They have a strong sense of belongingness to their ethnic group. They feel good about their cultural and ethnic background. They take pride in the ethnic group and their accomplishments and are active on organizations that mainly include their own ethnic group. They have a strong attachment to ethnic groups and participate in the group's cultural practices. Thus, it can be inferred that the respondents had strong affirmation and belongingness to their ethnic group. These are reflected in their responses "*Na Ivatan ako*" (I am a true Ivatan).

A *low acculturation* in ethnic identity had some connection to their identity and how they tend to identify themselves from a group. According to Phinney (1992), a strong ethnic identity while also identifying with the new society is considered an integrated or bicultural identity. Along the same line is the outcome of acculturation. Berry (2005) mentioned that "integration takes place when certain aspects of original culture (i.e. language) is retained and at the same time fully adopting the host culture." In this sense, the Ivatan women are not bicultural since they have a strong ethnic identity and have not fully adopted the host's culture. The respondents would emphasize that they cannot be identified with the non-Ivatan ethnic group, but they can relate to them. The Batanes Born of Fire (2011) mentioned that "among the Ivatans in Batanes, they are clannish and cluster together in kin groups." This closely knit nature of Ivatan community would explain that after 50 years of settlement, they still have a strong ethnic identity.

It can be seen that they rated a *low acculturation* in the role of ethnicity in their lives. This item shows that the respondents have an apparent concept of the role of ethnicity in their lives. Although, during the interview, they would be thinking deeply before answering the question, they find it intriguing how their ethnicity matters. They rated *moderate acculturation* as spending some time to learn more about the culture and history of their ethnic group. One respondent said, "*Busy sa bukid*" (I'm busy tending the farm), thus, they do not have time to know more about their culture. They have *moderate acculturation* and spend more time with other ethnic groups. This indicates that they usually spend some time with other groups. Ivatans are known to be a peace loving people. They would try to maintain good interpersonal relationships. For some respondents, it is important to be with other ethnic groups as long as it is for the good of both groups. As observed, the respondents are not strict about being with other ethnic groups. In summary, the acculturation level of the Ivatans, based on their language and ethnic identity, is *low*. The standard deviation indicated that their ratings were homogeneous, meaning they did not disperse much from the mean.

Conclusions

The first generation Ivatan women have settled in Malinao, Kalilangan, Bukidnon for over 30 years. The majority of the women consider themselves farmers. Having retained their demographic characteristics, it is concluded that a person with a very strong sense of ethnic identity, would not be easily influenced by the culture of other groups.

The Ivatan women still frequently use the Ivatan language in their daily activities. They possess a strong sense of affirmation and belongingness to their ethnic group. They have low acculturation levels in terms of language and ethnic identity. Having retained only some of their enduring practices and Ivatan language, it is concluded that the preservation and transmission of culture are affected by interpersonal and intrapersonal interactions and advanced technology.

Recommendations

A sociological approach in the study of women is found to be compelling in the study of migrant Ivatan women. The impact of their acculturation may have influenced their role as custodians of culture and, thus, may fall short of the group's expectations. On this note, the researcher would recommend further research on the group, especially on their language and intangible and tangible culture, which are waiting to be discovered. A more in depth and thorough assessment and collection of their intangible culture is also recommended. They may have forgotten some but given enough time it can be revealed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares that in conducting this study, utmost care was taken to ensure compliance with ethical standards. All participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement in the research. They were informed of their right to withdraw from the study without consequence. The anonymity of the respondents was strictly maintained, with no identifying information disclosed in any reports or publications resulting from this study.

The well-being of the respondents was a priority throughout the research process. During data collection and analysis, measures were implemented to safeguard their physical, emotional, and psychological welfare. No conflicts of interest were present or impacted the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and proper citations and references were employed to acknowledge the work of others. There was no bias in the interpretation of the findings; data was analyzed objectively and reported accurately.

The results of this study are intended solely for research purposes, with no intention of misrepresentation or misuse.

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